

Parasitization of azolla caterpillar, Mandya, India.

Sep 1983	Parasitization (%)		
	<i>Apanteles</i> sp.	<i>B. excarinata</i>	<i>Xanthopimpla</i> sp.
Wk1	30	8	1
Wk2	35	9	1
Wk3	43	11	0
Wk4	50	14	4
Mean	40	10	1

aquatic larva forms a tubular structure by folding the azolla and feeds on azolla fronds.

Infestation was slight in Jul, but by Sep 40-45% of the azolla was infested with the caterpillars.

Well-developed larvae and pupae were collected in the field at weekly intervals to identify natural enemies. Larval parasitization by *Apanteles* sp.

(Braconidae) ranged from 30 to 50% with a mean monthly 40% (see table).

The pupal parasite *Brachymeria excarinata* Gahan (Chalcididae) affected 8 to 14% (av 10%) of the caterpillars. *Xanthopimpla* sp. (Ichneumonidae) parasitism was about 1%.

Caterpillar population declined after Sep because large snail populations killed the azolla. □

Wet season population fluctuation of whitebacked planthopper (WBPH) in West Java

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WBPH *Sogatella furcifera* Horvath is a serious rice pest in Karawang, where Cisadane is the most popular variety. We recorded WBPH population fluctuations in 1983-84 wet season in Tunggakjati.

Biweekly sampling was by sweep net, 25 strokes with 10 replications. Captured insects were observed under a binocular microscope and WBPH and its spider predators were counted. At early growth stages, WBPH population was low and less than the spider population. WBPH population peaked 62 d after transplanting, then decreased. The spider population followed a similar trend (see figure).

WBPH and spiders /25 strokes

Number of WBPH and spiders at different ages of Cisadane rice in 1983-84 wet season. Karawang, West Java, Indonesia.

Parasite complex of yellow stem borer (YSB)

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We studied the parasite complex of YSB *Scirpophaga incertulas* (Walk.) from May 1980 to Jun 1982 at TNAU Coimbatore.

Egg and larval YSB parasites at TNAU Coimbatore, India.

Parasite	Family	Host stage affected	Mean parasitism (%)	Month of activity
<i>Tetrastichus schoenobii</i> Ferriere	Eulophidae	Egg	47	Dec-Jan
<i>Telenomus rowani</i> Gahan	Scelionidae	Egg	6	Oct
<i>Telenomus</i> sp.	Scelionidae	Egg	1	Jan-Feb
<i>Scelio</i> sp.	Scelionidae	Egg	1	Jan-Feb
<i>Exoryza schoenobii</i> Wilkinson	Braconidae	Larva	10	Jan-Feb
<i>Rhaconotus</i> sp.	Braconidae	Larva	3	Jan-Feb
<i>Amauromorpha</i> <i>accepta methathoracica</i>	Ichneumonidae	Larva	1	Sep

Four egg and four larval parasites were observed (see table). Egg parasitization was greater (47%) than larval parasitization (10%).

Tetrastichus schoenobii (Ferriere) was the predominant egg parasite. It peaked with 47% parasitism in Dec-Jan. *Apanteles schoenobii* (Wilk) was the predominant larval parasite. □

Pest control and management

WEEDS

Effect of time of herbicide application on rices of different durations

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We studied in 1983 the selectivity and effectiveness of four preemergence

herbicides in a lowland nursery at TNAU. Soil was a clay loam.

Short-duration IR50 (105 d), medium-duration Co 43 (135 d), and long-duration Ponmani (165 d) were the main plot treatments. Herbicides – 1 kg butachlor/ha, 1 kg thiobencarb/ha, 0.5 kg oxadiazon/ha, and 1 kg pendimethalin/ha – were applied at 5 and 8 d after sowing and compared to an untreated control. The field was puddled and pre-

Effect of time of herbicide application (DS)^a and rice duration in a lowland rice nursery, Coimbatore, India.

Variety	Butachlor 1 kg/ha		Thiobencarb 1 kg/ha		Oxadiazon 0.5 kg/ha		Pendimethalin 1 kg/ha		Control
	5 DS	8 DS	5 DS	8 DS	5 DS	8 DS	5 DS	8 DS	
<i>Echinochloa crus-galli</i> (no./0.04 m ²) at 20 DS									
IR50	0.16	0.50	0	0.50	0	0.50	0.16	1.16	3.50
Ponmani	0	0	0.33	0	0	0	0.16	0.50	4.82
Co 43	0	0.60	0	0.16	0	0.16	0.33	1.16	4.33
Mean	0.05	0.36	0.11	0.22	0	0.22	0.22	0.94	4.22
<i>Cyperus difformis</i> (no./0.04 m ²) at 20 DS									
IR50	0.50	0.58	0	0.58	0	0.92	0.75	1.25	4.08
Ponmani	0	0	0.16	0	0	0.16	0.75	0.93	5.08
Co 43	0	1.13	0	0.25	0	0.08	0.83	1.25	4.16
Mean	0.17	0.57	0.05	0.28	0	0.39	0.76	1.14	4.44
<i>Rice height</i> (cm)									
IR50	15.7	17.7	16.3	19.2	14.2	17.0	15.7	17.4	19.9
Ponmani	16.3	20.0	17.1	18.4	17.8	19.6	17.0	18.9	19.4
Co 43	16.1	18.0	17.0	20.0	15.4	18.5	17.2	18.5	20.0
Mean	16.0	18.6	16.8	19.2	15.8	18.9	16.6	18.3	19.8
<i>Rice population</i>									
IR50	65.5	106.5	92.5	132.5	75.0	106.5	111.5	122.0	136.0
Ponmani	78.0	121.0	118.5	136.0	97.5	149.0	83.0	111.5	155.5
Co 43	87.5	122.5	100.0	139.5	77.0	138.0	85.5	120.0	135.0
Mean	77.0	116.6	103.7	136.0	83.2	131.2	93.3	117.8	142.2

^aDS = days after sowing.

	Treatment		Varieties		Interaction	
	SE	CD	SE	CD	SE	CD
1.	0.020	0.056	0.011	0.032	0.034	0.096
2.	0.058	0.163	0.033	0.094	0.100	0.283
3.	0.570	1.621	0.330	0.901	0.984	2.841
4.	0.820	2.330	0.474	1.340	1.421	4.030

germinated seeds were sown 1 d after leveling. Emulsifiable concentrate formulations were mixed with sand (2 kg/1,000 m²) and applied uniformly in 2.5-cm-deep water.

Mean weed data from the nursery (see table) indicated population of annual weeds in the herbicide-treated plots was from 0 to 0.94/0.04 m² for *Echinochloa crus-galli* and from 0 to 1.14/0.04 m² for *Cyperus difformis*. Counts were 4.22 to 4.44/0.04 m² in control plots. The herbicides effectively controlled weed growth. Eighth-d application was more selective than fifth-d application. Selectivity was low with fifth-d application of butachlor or oxadiazon to IR50. □

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Pest control and management OTHER PESTS

Influence of rate and time of carbofuran application to control root-knot nematodes in upland rice

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Root-knot nematode *Meloidogyne incognita* (Kofoid and White) Chitwood causes poor seedling establishment and low rice yields. The effect is more severe under upland conditions. We tested carbofuran for nematode control in a greenhouse experiment.

OS6 seeds were planted in 4 litres of steam-sterilized loamy soil and inoculated

with 1000 root-knot nematode eggs recovered from galled roots of *Celosia* sp. Carbofuran was applied at three rates at

different times (see table) in three replications. Fifty days after planting (DAP), galls and soil nematode population were

Effect of carbofuran on root-knot nematodes in rice, Ibadan, Nigeria.

Treatment	13 DAP		35 DAP	
	Galling index ^a	Nematode population	Galling index ^a	Nematode population
No nematicide	2.7	1738	2.7	1738
Carbofuran 10G 1 kg ai/ha	1.3	837**	1.7	888**
Carbofuran 10G 2 kg ai/ha	1.3	213**	1.3	1475*
Carbofuran 10G 3 kg ai/ha	1.0	238**	1.7	250**
LSD	1% = 93.78		5% = 67.57	

^a0 = no galling system

1 = less than ¼ of root system with small galls

2 = less than ½ of root system with small galls

3 = less than ½ of root system with medium galls

4 = more than ½ of root system with medium galls